

PRABAHARAN MANOHARAN

Profile Summary:

- ❖ 13 years of total Experience in the field of **Mechanical Engineering**.

Core Qualifications

- ❖ Hands on experience in 3D Mechanical Designing using **Solid work, Inventor Autodesk, AutoCAD**
- ❖ 2D Drafting, 3D Modeling, Manufacturing
- ❖ Good knowledge of designing application based grippers for **KUKA** Industrial Robots
- ❖ Working experience in the field of Quality control & assurance, Production, **CMM programming, CNC Milling, SIMPRO** and **Octopuz** Simulation.
- ❖ Affinity towards learning New Technologies.
- ❖ Working for results with dedication & determination.
- ❖ Demonstrated abilities in Production Shop Maintenance, Erection & Commissioning, trouble Shooting, and Safety.
- ❖ An Excellent grasp of Engineering and design principles.
- ❖ A creative, logical approach for generating new ideas and solutions, with the ability to transition through to part development

Professional Experience:

Mar-2015 - **Project Designer -DIGI ROBOTICS TECHNOLOGY FZ**, Dubai.

Present

- Constructed CAD models in line with customer CAD standards using Solidwork-2017 & Inventor-2017, with AutoCAD.
- Designed and Developed concept based on client requirements and realize the concept related to Automation and Robotics System.
- Designed New Jig and Fixture for Industrial Robotics Applications.
- Developed Automation step to in-Cooperate with Advanced Robotics Applications for Mechanical Industries.
- Coordinated the development of Parts drawings, including CAD drawing, through other drawings, internal or outsourced to comprehensively manage the complete design of the tools that are assigned.
- Prepared and Authored user manuals for the developed products for customers.
- Prepare layout and details drawing of design as required to project timelines.
- Reviewed and studied customer specifications engineering schematic and other data in order to determine the design procedure needs to generate and release digital and or hand copy, printouts related to the engineering and manufacturing requirements.

Aug-2011 - **Mechanical Design Engineer -JCY HDD TECHNOLOGY SDN BHD**, Malaysia.

Feb-2015

- Part modeling Computer Hard disk 2.5" and 3.5"
- Developed Mould and Mould Accessories, HPDC (High Pressure Die Casting).
- Developed MAGMA SOFT 4.4 & 5.2 Casting Flow Simulation and Analysis; 2.5" and 3.5".
- Experienced in Part Single Cavity and Six Cavity Mould designed in Solidwork-2015.
- Coordinated design/purchase, shop/assembly team on designed products.
- Designed and developed **Trimming Die Machine**.
- Inspection, testing and evaluation off project sites, preparing on site reports and possible suggestions. or solutions for improvements.

- Designed 2.5” & 3.5” Hard disk Machining Fixture.
- Prepared Gauges and Fixture design.
- Performed Fit Tolerance Analysis of core parts of NPD Jaw crusher.

Oct-2009 – **CMM Programmer -JCY HDD TECHNOLOGY SDN BHD**, Johor Bahru, Malaysia.

Aug-2011

- Responsible for all CMM programming and operations performed on CMM's
- Coordinated data files with Engineering and developed CMM programming and reporting standards.
- Trained personnel in CMM operator mode.
- Standardized program storage, reported storage, all file names and CMM features.
- Prepared backup CMM accessories probes, extensions and all phases of CMM hardware.
- 3d Scan Chamber Molds/Cylinder Heads, then develop in Next Engine/Rapid Works
- Programmed Geopak CMM Mitutoyo 776 machine with basic understanding of GD&T

Mar-2008 – **Senior Quality Control Supervisor -JRE VALUES & PUMPS (P)LTD**, Coimbatore, INDIA

July-2009

- Supervised and coordinated activities of workers engaged in inspecting incoming materials, in process molded valves components, and finished fabricated pumps products to ensure adherence to company quality standards and customer specifications.
- Directed audit activities commensurate to production schedules.
- Developed monthly reports showing inspection and audit performance and improvement opportunities.
- Evaluated and recommend alternative auditing procedures for continuous improvement.
- Supported production leads and operators for interpretation and methods following set STD.
- Maintained working production component's knowledge and associate next tier application.

Aug-2007 – **Development Engineer -JRE VALUES & PUMPS (P)LTD**, Coimbatore, INDIA

Feb-2008

- Served as a team's Mechanical Engineer for major development projects or multiple simultaneous projects.
- Ensured that Engineering Design activities are coordinated per the development procedure.
- Worked closely with electrical and software engineers, designing with system-wide perspective.
- Lead, participate in or support the following product development activities:
- Concept, planning, design and execution stages of major new products or product enhancements
- Prototyping and testing concept designs and initial engineering builds
- Assisted in project planning and provide mechanical design leadership in project execution.

June-2004 – **Senior Production Supervisor -JRE VALUES & PUMPS (P)LTD**, Coimbatore, INDIA

July -2007

- Identified issues in team and provide continuous support to all members according to operating standards on everyday basis.
- Supervised effective working of production personnel and prepare effective production schedules and ensure compliance to all company policies.
- Maintained records of all data attendance and provided effective training to all staff members.
- Coordinated with equipment and process teams and ensured compliance to all protocols and maintained product quality.
- Administered work according to QR/QC principles and recommended strategies to improve processes.
- To ensure that Health and Safety rules and regulations are adhered to during the shift and all matters relating to this are dealt with using the resources within the company in line with the companies' health and Safety policy.

April-2004 – *A/C Plant Technician - BHARAT SHANGAR NIGAM LTD*, Kumbakonam, INDIA

Nov -2003 - Contractor – *Marktroniks*, Mayiladuthurai, India.

- Responded to Facility Service Work Orders. Responses primarily were for issues with the HVAC systems.
- Completed major repairs and in-depth preventative maintenance as well as other facility maintenance services.
- Interpreted compliance requirements and ensures standardization of work.
- Identified opportunities for process/system improvements and implemented them.
- Developed log readings from critical equipment and took appropriate corrective actions to minimize system outages.

In-Plant Training:

- Has undergone Industrial Training in *GREENFILED MOTORS & PUMPS*, INDIA from June - 2003 to Oct - 2003
- Has undergone Industrial Training in *MAHENDRA PUMPS (P) LTD.*, INDIA from Dec - 2001 to April - 2002

Educational Qualification:

Course	- <i>Diploma in Mechanical Engineering, (Sandwich) - Aug 2000 to Oct-2003</i>
College	- Coimbatore Institute of Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India
Course	- <i>Secondary School of Leaving Certificate (SSLC) – October -1999</i>
School	- Government Higher Secondary School, Rasipuram, Tamilnadu, India

Technical Software's Skills

❖ Solid Works	-	3D Modeling, Drafting	- 8 years
❖ Inventor Professional	-	3D Modeling, Drafting	- 5 years
❖ AutoCAD	-	2D Drafting, Modeling	- 12 years
❖ Octopuz 1.6	-	Simulation at Robotics	- 06 Month
❖ Magma 5.2	-	HPDC Simulation	- 3 years
❖ MCOSMOS- (CMM)	-	Geopak V2.4 R10 Programming	- 2 years
❖ KUKA Simpro 2.2.2	-	Simulation at Robotics	- 2 years
❖ KUKA Vision Pro(R)	-	Robotics Programming	- 06 Month

Technical Proficiency:

❖ Description	-	Robotics Programming & Vision Tech	- June 2015
Organized by	-	KUKA India (P) Ltd, India	
❖ Description	-	Simpro 2.2.2 Robotics Simulation	- May 2015
Organized by	-	KUKA India (P) Ltd, India	
❖ Description	-	Magmas 5.2 & HPDC Simulation	- July to Sep-2013
Organized by	-	MAGMA Engineering Asia (P) Ltd, Singapore.	
❖ Description	-	Introduction to Design of Experiment	- July 11&12 -2013
Organized by	-	Neville Clarke, Malaysia.	
❖ Description	-	Advanced Part Modeling Course (SW)	-Sep 2012
Organized by	-	IME CAD/CAM Training Center Sdn Bhd, Malaysia.	
❖ Description	-	CNC Turning and Milling	- Jan 2008

Organized by	-	Sethu Ideal CNC Training Centre, India.	
❖ Description	-	AutoCAD	- Oct 2002
Organized by	-	V.R.E. T Training Centre, India	
❖ Description	-	Diploma in Computer Technology	- Nov to May 2000
Organized by	-	Small Industries Development Organization, India.	

Project

Designed and Realization of Automation Fixture for Robotics Welding for an Aluminum Doors and Window Frames. (MAY 2015 – JAN 2016)

- Design and developed fully Automated Welding Fixture in cooperated with Robotics Welding for an Aluminum Doors and Window Frame Fabrication. Unit @ Saudi Arabia

Design and Fabrication of Robotics Welding Fixture for Doors Hinges (FEB 2015 – JUN 2016)

- Robotics Welding Fixture for Hinges on Steel Doors Frames. There were three positioning unit with Advanced Pneumatic Rotary units which guided the Hinges on right position with repeat ability. All units were driven by high precision ball screw units with stepper motor. It was a fully Automatic Robotic Jig associated with KUKA 3-Axis positioner and KR 30 Robot welding. Unit @ Saudi

Design and Fabrication of Robotics Welding Jig Scaffolding Frames (SEP 2016 – DEC 2016)

- Consisted of Semi-Automatics Welding Jig for welding of Different Scaffolding Frames in-cooperated with KUKA 3-Axis Positioner and KR30 Robot along with Pneumatic clamps which was operated with the help of PLC Programs. Unit @ Ajman, Dubai.

Personal Profile:

Current Number	:	(+971) 0504546587, 0564425811 - Dubai
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Grab CAD	:	https://grabcad.com/prabha.mano-1
Linkedin.com	:	https://www.linkedin.com/in/prabha-mano-940252b9/
Contact Address	:	Tower -Lakeside- A, 5 th Floor, Flat No-511, IMPZ, Near Grand Gaya Hotel, Dubai

Reference

Available on request.

Declaration:

I consider myself familiar with **MECHANICAL ENGINEERING** aspects. I am also confident of my ability to work in a team. I hereby declare that the all information furnished above is true to the Best of my Knowledge.

Place:

Date:

M. PRABAHARAN